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Pedagogical Strategies, Approaches and Methodologies to Support Numeracy in Primary Education

A Review of the Literature

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Summary

- *Conceptual understanding and procedural fluency* is promoted through providing opportunities for children to engage in making sense of the mathematics rather than employing procedural methods by rote.
 - *Problem based learning* supports children's active participation in the process of solving mathematical problems from the outset. It fosters collaborative learning, encourages knowledge retention and conceptual development, a positive attitude towards mathematics and leads to higher mathematical gains.
 - *Number sense* methodologies develop children's agency and ownership of mathematics, enhances mathematical discourse, enables meaningful connections across concepts to be made, thus supporting flexibility and fluency.
 - *Mathematical writing* promotes engagement with mathematical processes and an opportunity for children to creatively demonstrate their knowledge and understanding of mathematical concepts. It is most effective when embedded as an integral part of teaching and learning and is of particular benefit in catering for the needs of high-achieving students.
- *Interventions* of a small-group nature, with hands-on learning, on a regular basis, have a significant positive impact on targeted mathematical concepts.
 - Bridging the gap caused by socio-economic factors such as poverty and/or marginalisation requires specific and targeted interventions. A focus on number sense approaches and conceptual understanding starting in the early years must underpin initiatives in this area.
 - *Learners with English as an additional language and students with reading difficulties* require authentic assessment that distinguishes between literacy competence and mathematics performance. Interventions to improve mathematics performance should have a broader focus than improving mathematical language.
 - *Homogeneous ability grouping* does not appear to benefit learners at any level of achievement and in fact appears to disadvantage those who are achieving at a lower level. *Gender* has no significant impact on children's mathematical abilities or achievement.
- *Representations* facilitate children to develop their own ways to model the mathematics they encounter.
 - *Resources*, both concrete and digital, have a meaningful, positive impact on mathematics learning, particularly in relation to higher order mathematical skills, such as problem solving, mathematising and reasoning.
 - *Children's literature* can represent mathematical concepts in a number of formats, visually, symbolically, and contextually. Making meaningful connections between different types of mathematical representations supports conceptual understanding and increases students' mathematical achievement throughout primary school.
- *Parental perspectives and engagement* is an important indicator of children's attitudes towards mathematics and their achievement.

Recommendations

Curriculum and the Learning Experience

In order to develop positive attitudes and motivation to learn, mathematics needs to be presented as a sense-making activity (DES, 2011; ETI & DES, 2015; NCCA, 2017) to which children can;

- bring creative approaches, engage in both problem solving and problem posing (Hoth et al., 2017; Bicer et al., 2021)
- work in heterogeneous collaborative groups to problem solve (Merritt et al., 2017; Drunk et al., 2018),
- explore multiple solutions and solution pathways to build conceptual understanding (Boaler, 2015; ETI & DES, 2015; Cirillio et al., 2016; Cason et al., 2019),
- have agency and ownership in producing their own mathematical content and engaging in mathematical writing (Firmender et al., 2017; Trakulphadetkrai et al., 2019; Graham et al., 2020; NCCA, 2020).

Children need to be active in their learning rather than passive recipients of knowledge (NCCA, 2017 & 2020), in ways such as;

- problem solving and mathematical talk and discussion (Merritt et al., 2017),
- using resources and representations, both concrete and digital, as well as children's literature, as an integral part of their mathematical experiences (Carbonneau et al., 2013; Cirillio et al., 2016; Ginsburg, 2016; Kul et al., 2018; Edelman et al., 2019),
- being physically active and combining play-based approaches with playful teaching and learning (Dooley et al., 2014; EEF, 2018; Vetter et al., 2019)
- generating their own representations of mathematics, engaging with exploratory digital environments (Bryun & Joung, 2018; Sokolowski, 2018).

Assessment and Evaluation

Best pedagogical and assessment practices:

- put the needs of all learners to the fore and provide all children with the opportunity to engage with high-quality mathematics and develop their own mathematical ideas (Merritt et al., 2017; Cason et al., 2019; Trakulphadetkrai et al., 2019; NCCA, 2020),
- promote rich and accommodating inclusive differentiated strategies targeted to the individual needs of the learner, as part of a whole school approach (Clements & Sarama, 2014; Deunk et al., 2018),
- are cognisant of and take measures to counteract exterior factors that may influence mathematical performance such as low socioeconomic background, English as an additional language, reading difficulty or maths anxiety (Castro-Olivo et al., 2011; Ramirez et al., 2013; Alt, 2014; Cason et al., 2019; Powell et al., 2020).

Students with Additional Learning Needs

Interventions to challenge or support children at different achievement levels should;

- begin as early as possible in the child's schooling, be of longer rather than shorter duration; and avoid homogeneous ability grouping or streaming (Rolfhus et al., 2013; Peltier et al., 2017, Deunk et al., 2018; Stevens et al., 2018),
- have an explicit focus on developing mathematical understanding (Alt et al., 2013;

Stevens et al., 2018; Powell et al., 2020; Arizemendi et al., 2021).

Enabling Parents and Communities

Opportunities need to be provided for collaboration and communication among practitioners and researchers.

- It is recommended that parents are encouraged to become involved in all aspects of their child's education, especially mathematics (Ramirez et al., 2013; Fan et al., 2017; Choi & Han, 2020).

Pedagogical Strategies, Approaches and Methodologies to Support Numeracy at Primary Level

In the first four years after the *Literacy and Numeracy Strategy* (DES, 2011) was launched there was a significant improvement in Irish pupils' mean mathematics scores as assessed by Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) and National Assessments of English Reading and Mathematics (NAMER) (Perkins & Clerkin, 2020; Shiel et al., 2014). However, this rise in improvement has now levelled off suggesting that there has been little to no change in mathematical attainment recorded since. Findings further indicate that whilst lower-achieving pupils are performing relatively well, highest-achieving pupils are underperforming in mathematics (Perkins & Clerkin, 2020). Moreover, in the *Interim Review* of the *Strategy*, it was recommended that "a stronger emphasis is needed on numeracy in primary schools" (DES, 2017, p. 36). Thus, whereas this report draws on recent research to exemplify "cooperative learning, differentiated learning, active learning and problem-solving activity, which we know not only contribute to more effective learning but increase learners' participation in and enjoyment of the learning process" (DES, 2011, p. 43), it goes further to identify what "different approaches are required for Mathematics in general" (DES, 2017, p. 36). In so doing, a broad conceptualisation of Mathematics is provided rather than a fine-grained analysis of individual mathematical concepts so that the pedagogies identified can be utilised across all areas of mathematics.

Thus this report is pertinent in considering how best to shape children's mathematical experiences so as to develop fundamental knowledge and skills and to build mathematics learning environments that are developmentally appropriate and effective (Clements & Sarama, 2014). The report goes further in addressing factors that can influence attitudes and motivations that are "vital for progression" in mathematics (DES, 2011, p. 43). Thus, a synthesis of systematic reviews is provided to showcase "appropriate and evidence-based pedagogical approaches and strategies to foster engagement, ownership and challenge while connecting with children's life experiences and their interests" (National Council for Curriculum and Assessment [NCCA], 2020, p. 6). A range of learners and consideration of other contributing factors to think about when planning mathematical experiences that support numeracy development for all learners in primary schools are detailed.

Research Question

What pedagogical strategies, approaches and methodologies support numeracy development for all learners in primary schools?

Narrative Report

Developing Mathematical Proficiency

“Mathematical proficiency encompasses conceptual understanding, procedural fluency, adaptive reasoning, strategic competence, and productive disposition” (NCCA, 2017, p. 21). In this section, the research synthesises two pedagogical strategies utilised to develop mathematical proficiency, namely problem-based learning and sense-making approaches. These practices support children in acquiring a deep understanding of mathematics rather than the heavy reliance on memorisation of rules and application of procedures by rote. The learning environment presents multiple paths to solving mathematics with no one clear, unique approach or answer thus enabling the learner to be creative, make choices, assumptions, and decisions (Cirillio et al., 2016).

Problem-Based Learning

Generally based on Deweyan ideology and thinking, a range of definitions of problem-based learning (PBL) exist. Despite differences in definitions, most models of PBL have a number of commonalities including beginning the learning process with a problem which requires the students to learn by doing, prior to any formal instruction. The teacher is viewed as the guide as opposed to the custodian of information. Merritt et al., (2017) conducted a systematic review to explore its effectiveness with students in early elementary to grade 8 (ages 3–14) in mathematics. All of the studies reviewed, designed their PBL instruction based on small groups (4-6 students), and emphasised collaboration skills to resolve the given problem together. Studies which focused on academic achievement reported the vast majority (87.5%) of students had achieved mathematical gains as a result of PBL instruction (Merritt et al., 2017). Of the studies centered on knowledge retention, 75% indicated that students in the PBL group had better knowledge retention than the control group. Furthermore, all studies that examined conceptual development and attitudes reported all students having a positive conceptual mathematical development and a more positive

attitude towards mathematics as a result of engaging in PBL (Merritt et al., 2017). The evidence presented in these meta-analyses positions PBL as an effective pedagogical tool in mathematical teaching and learning.

Number Sense and Sense-Making Approaches

Number sense approaches enhance learners' "number fluency and accuracy" (Education and Training Inspectorate (ETI) & Department of Education and Skills (DES), 2015, p. 15). They enable children to compose and decompose numbers, to calculate flexibly and informally drawing on patterns, known facts and number strategies, which leads to engagement with number from a sense-making perspective. They allow children to see the interconnectedness of numbers and to draw on a select number of rules and strategies in connection with using familiar number facts acquired by practice to help them quickly and competently perform calculations on numbers, not limited to single digit numbers.

It is generally recognised that fluency with number facts ('tables') is a fundamental skill in mathematics which supports children in more complex calculations (Boaler, 2015). The traditional rote learning or drill and practice approaches have been shown to serve children poorly, as many children struggle to commit such a large body of facts to memory. Cason et al. (2019) support the idea that mastery of number facts is fundamental to children's success in mathematics, and are unequivocal in finding support for an approach that is rooted in a foundation of conceptual understanding. In their analysis of studies concerned with the development of number competency, Cason et al. (2019) reported on effect sizes in earlier grades (up to second grade) that were approximately twice as large as those in later grades. This would support an early focus on number sense. Gains in pupil competence can be substantial in earlier grades. Implications of this finding would be support for pedagogy built on developing strong conceptual foundations, and little support for drill-and-practice or rote-learning approaches.

Supporting Engagement

"Children are active and demonstrate agency as the capacity to act independently and to make choices about and in their learning. Curriculum experiences provide them with opportunities for decision-making, creativity and collaboration" (NCCA, 2020, p. 6).

Mathematical Writing

“Children develop their mathematical proficiency through engaging with processes such as connecting, communication, reasoning, argumentation, justifying, representing, problem solving, and generalising” (NCCA, 2017, p. 28). One creative approach that can be utilised across all class levels in the primary school classroom to promote these processes is that of mathematical writing. Writing provides an opportunity for students to “make meaningful connections between the different key elements of mathematics learning by themselves” (Trakulphadetkrai et al., 2019, p. 210). It further allows children to demonstrate their knowledge and understanding of a mathematical concept in a way that is explicit for their peers and teacher to read or listen to and thus gives the teacher an opportunity to then “address any misconception” found in the writing or to ask questions “in order to extend the children’s mathematical thinking further” (Trakulphadetkrai et al., 2019, p. 210).

Graham et al. (2020) report on a systematic review of 56 studies on the effects of writing on learning with 21 of those studies focusing on mathematics. They outline the many formats that writing for learning can take in the mathematics classroom. Journaling was the format favoured in the majority of studies (52%) and is one that is promoted by the Professional Development Support for Teachers (PDST, n.d.) in exploring problem solving as a central methodology across the mathematics curriculum (see [pdst.ie](https://www.pdst.ie) for an example of journal prompts). However, Graham et al. detail a finer-grained analysis of what writing for learning might look like in the classroom and report on a further 29% of the mathematics studies analysed that use informative writing (e.g. summarising information, explaining how to carry out an activity, personalising information learned, and sharing information about a topic etc.) to promote learning. Students also engaged in narrative writing to create story problems in mathematics. Argumentation was applied in one study in which students constructed written arguments for solving mathematical problems. Whereas in a further study in mathematics, the approach to writing involved creating a graphical representation of key concepts. Graham et al. (2020) went further in classifying these writing activities in relation to Bloom's (1956) taxonomy of learning outcomes designed to encourage higher-order thinking by building up from lower-order cognitive skills. No writing activity focused on the lowest level of building knowledge. Working up through the levels, the next level of comprehension was promoted in 20% of studies, application 15%, analysis 15%, synthesis 20%, and at the highest level evaluation of content information was promoted in 30% of the investigations. While it is recommended that all students engage in all types of writing, this pedagogy has specific implications for students who might be considered as gifted or talented

through fostering higher-order mathematical reasoning, discovery, and communication through the use of creative writing (Firmender et al., 2017).

Active Learning Environment

The broader benefits of including physical activity throughout the school day have been widely reported with “some evidence that physical whole-body movement and gestures may support the learning of mathematics, for example, moving along a physical number line, or jumping and clapping while counting” (Education Endowment Foundation (EEF), 2018, p. 20). Vetter et al., (2019) specifically focus on the links between physical activity and mathematical achievement in primary school aged children. A systematic literature review of the topic revealed 11 studies to be evaluated. Of which, there was a range in physical activity, variations from 10-15 minutes to 60 minute sessions. The physical activity incorporated basic movement skills such as jumping, hopping and skipping alongside the targeted mathematical component, such as multiplication facts, counting, fractions, and measurement. Mathematics scores were significantly better in the intervention group in six of 11 studies on at least one test (Vetter et al., 2019). The evidence presented in this research highlights the benefits for incorporating physical activity with mathematics learning, particularly in primary or elementary schools. It could also perhaps indicate that in more active environments, children are spending less time on individual generic seatwork involving the rote practice of procedures.

Mathematical Creativity

Traditionally, creativity was affiliated with the arts, although more recently, creativity is deemed to be one of the most crucial skills of the 21st century by policy makers, educators, and those within industry (Bicer et al., 2021). In the domain of mathematics classroom, the term *creativity* is often used with reference to the work of children in applying conceptual understanding to problem solving and problem posing (Hoth et al., 2017). In a meta-analysis over the past five decades, Bicer et al. (2021) examined the interrelationship between creative ability and mathematics achievement. In terms of mathematical creativity in the classroom, Bicer et al. (2021) determined that students’ creativity can be fostered through a range of interactions they have with teachers and peers. They classify creativity in terms of creative and meaningful insights experienced by students as they learn new concepts; from the experiences, actions and events they encounter in a mathematics classroom (Bischer et al., 2020). The results of this investigation indicate that there was an overall moderate and

positive relationship between K-12 students' mathematics achievement and their creative abilities ($r = .47, p < .05$) when measured on the Mathematical Creativity Test (MCT). The relationship was stronger when examined with mathematical creativity rather than with general creativity ($r = .53, p < .05$) and statistically more significant in elementary and middle school students than for high school students (Bicer et al., 2021). These findings indicate that there is a positive correlation between primary school children's creative abilities and mathematics achievement.

“Instead of seeing mathematics as ready-made knowledge to be transmitted, Freudenthal stressed the idea of mathematics as a human activity. Mathematics lessons should give students the “guided” opportunity to “re-invent” mathematics by doing it. This means that in mathematics education, the focal point should not be on mathematics as a closed system, but on the activity, on the process of mathematization” (van den Heuvel Panhuizen & Wijers, 2005, p. 288). Play-based pedagogy and playful approaches to mathematics teaching and learning is an effective creative strategy, especially in the early years of primary school. Participating and interacting in playful situations, mathematizing with the children and engaging in interactive mathematical discourse are all aspects of pedagogy which are essential for meaningful mathematical play-based experiences for children (Dooley et al., 2014). The implications of these findings is that primary educators should consider creative approaches when planning for mathematics teaching and learning.

Models of Mathematics

A model for a mathematical concept refers to any object, picture, or drawing that represents the concept or onto which the relationship for that concept can be imposed (van de Walle, 2007). Modelling mathematics describes using representations of mathematics to illustrate, discover and communicate mathematical concepts or ideas (Cirillio et al., 2016).

Representations

Representations can be considered to be the passive embodiment of mathematical concepts as objects which can be engaged with and manipulated in order to develop an understanding of the concepts. Examples include concrete materials, pictures and diagrams, tables, equations and forms or figures in two or three dimensions, as well as digital tools (Jitendra et al., 1998). Making use of various forms of representations and demonstrating understanding by moving between concrete, graphical and symbolic and verbal forms are key skills in mathematics (Ainsworth et al., 2002). Each particular representation will make some

aspect of mathematics explicit and at the same time may hide other aspects, and so it is recommended that learners have the opportunity to explore multiple representations of mathematics in order to construct a comprehensive understanding. The use of rich and multiple forms of representations has been found to be highly effective in supporting mathematical learning (Haas, 2005).

Sokolowski (2018), in his analysis of 13 studies on representation use in elementary classrooms, found support for the use of representations to aid children learn. An association between longer interventions and greater effect supports the frequent and extended use of representations in the classroom, while a greater effect with younger grades argues for their early introduction. All types of representations examined – concrete, pictorial, schemata - based, story contexts, and others, were of benefit to learners, with stronger effects observed up to Grade 3. It may be that post grade 3, content learning moves towards more abstract objectives which may be more difficult to represent concretely. Particularly effective was the use of concrete objects to teach geometry concepts. Findings suggest that supporting children to develop their own representations was the most effective. For problem-solving, schemata-based representations emerged as the most effective, allowing children to systematically analyse and devise solution methods to non-routine problems, drawing on their secure understanding of mathematical concepts derived from prior engagement with multiple models of representation.

Concrete Resources

The inclusion of physical manipulatives to support mathematics teaching has long been recognised and promoted (Burns, 1996; Ginsburg, 2016). Concrete objects, particularly everyday items, allow students to make connections between abstract mathematical concepts and the real world (Brown et al., 2009). Carbonneau et al., (2013) completed a meta-analysis of 55 independent studies on the efficacy of teaching mathematics using concrete objects. In terms of primary school children, the findings indicate medium to large effect sizes in favour of instructional strategies that use manipulatives when compared with abstract instruction. Moderate to large effect sizes were evidenced when students were measured on higher level outcomes, such as problem solving, transfer and justification (Carbonneau et al., 2013).

Kul et al. (2018) corroborate these findings, as a meta-analysis they conducted on the impact of educational material use on mathematics achievement found that using materials (both digital and concrete) in mathematics teaching and learning has a positive and high

influence on student achievement. In studies where both concrete and digital materials are used for teaching, effect sizes were particularly high and significant (Kul et al., 2018, p. 315). Pedagogically, they discovered whether engagement with the materials is applied to individual students, a small group of students or to all students, does not have a significant moderator effect and did not impact the effect size value (Kul et al., 2018). This evidence suggests that children's engagement with resources has a meaningful, positive impact on mathematics learning, particularly in relation to higher order mathematical skills, such as problem solving, mathematizing and reasoning. Whether the resources are concrete or digital; used individually or in small groups is not deemed to be significant, but when concrete and digital resources are used in tandem, further mathematical gains are achieved.

Digital Tools

For mathematical teaching and learning, physical materials enable students to develop their psychomotor learning skills as they engage their sense of touch (Olkun, 2003) alongside the development of mathematical concepts. However, teaching with digital materials can provide a greater flexibility for manipulation, as the learner can rotate, reshape and flex objects more readily in a virtual environment (Kul et al., 2018). It is unsurprising therefore that the use of such tools to support mathematical learning has become an international topic, in particular in the primary school classroom (Byun & Joung, 2018). Sokolowski et al. (2015) report on a systematic review of 24 studies where the focus was on improving students' problem-solving skills, mathematical modeling and concept formation through learners' use of computers to explore the relations between a given word problem's variables in the attempt to mathematize and solve it. The objective of the research was augmented to focus on comparing more traditional teacher-guided methods of teaching problem solving and explorations to ones using digital technology. It was deduced that 70% of students who engaged with mathematical concepts through exploratory computerised environments scored higher on assessments than those who learned the same concept using traditional textbook materials. Whereas the effect size was highest for those students in middle school (grades 6 to 8), the effect sizes in the other grades (1 to 5) also showed a moderate magnitude. Furthermore, higher effect sizes were reported in cases where students were given the opportunity to apply already learned mathematics concepts in novel situations but not in cases where new concepts were being explored and applied thus illustrating that exploratory computerised environments cannot replace good teaching.

A systematic review of 22 studies where digital game based learning was used in the context of teaching elementary school students was conducted by Byun and Joung (2018). Most studies focused on the affective dimensions of learning mathematics such as students' motivation and attitudes with positive reports on the effect of increasing students' persistence with mathematical problem solving as part of the game context. Whereas a productive disposition is one of the five key components of developing mathematical proficiency, the use of digital games to actually promote achievement in mathematics learning is inconclusive (Byun & Joung, 2018). This could be due to the fact that most of the games reviewed in many of the studies benefitted procedural fluency only comprising what could best be described as predominantly gamified versions of paper-based drill-and-practice worksheets which do not promote the kind of higher order thinking skills required for solving more complex, open problems. In other words, repeating simple calculations is not enough to develop conceptual understanding, adaptive reasoning and strategic competence, which are inherently necessary for a student to develop mathematical proficiency (NCCA, 2017). This might explain why the overall effect size of digital game based learning in mathematics is quite low and that there may be other, more effective ways for students to learn mathematics (Byun & Joung, 2018).

Children's Literature

Using storybooks in mathematics teaching and learning has a number of reported benefits, including increasing student motivation; enhancing student metacognition; providing opportunities for mathematical discourse or mathematizing, and encouraging children to make personal connections with mathematical concepts (Trakulphadetkrai et al., 2019; Gaston, 2008; Ward, 2005). Edelman et al., (2019) conducted a systematic review on the use of children's literature in mathematics teaching and learning over a 25-year period. They found the use of children's literature in mathematics teaching and learning increased student achievement, not only in the early years of primary school but throughout. The use of children's literature in a sixth grade classroom increased the use of mathematical vocabulary and communication (Edelman et al., 2019). In the early years of primary school, there was an increase in mathematical discourse, mathematical vocabulary and communication after engaging in children's literature. The findings from this extensive review indicate that children's literature and storybooks should be incorporated into mathematics teaching and learning throughout primary school.

Inclusive Education and Diversity

When planning for mathematics teaching and learning in primary schools, it is essential to consider all learners. Classrooms are populated by children with diverse abilities and needs, and good teaching must take cognisance of this and ensure that appropriate support and challenge is offered as needed. Inclusive teaching practices ensure “that the starting point for learning reflects the needs and interests of the learner” (DES, 2011, p. 43). “Inclusive education provides for equity of opportunity and participation in children’s learning. Inclusive education celebrates diversity and responds to the uniqueness of every child” (NCCA, 2020, p. 6).

Differentiation

Differentiation can be considered to be the practice of modifying content, pedagogy, activities and resources to cater for the diverse needs of pupils, and it is recognised as a highly skilled aspect of teaching (Tomlinson et al., 2003). In looking at the effects of differentiation practices on learners at low, medium and high levels of mathematical achievement, Deunk et al. (2018) examined whether homogeneous ability grouping, computer assisted differentiation practices, and contexts where differentiation was part of a broader programme or school reform. Their findings indicated that homogeneous ability grouping, whether in-class or between-class, did not result in positive effects for any of the ability groups, and indeed showed a negative effect for low achieving pupils. The use of computer-assisted contexts where differentiation was situated as part of a programme or whole-school approach did show small positive effects of $d = +0.290$ and $d = +0.296$ respectively. The authors speculate that these positive effects may be the result of teacher support, professional development or collaboration in devising and implementing these strategies.

The Role of Mathematics Interventions in Raising Numeracy Standards

Targeted mathematical interventions have been found to support students' learning and development. For instance, Rolfhus et al. (2013) report on the first large-scale effectiveness of the intervention, *Number Rockets*, targeted at students who were deemed at risk in terms of mathematics. This small group, supplementary intervention, met three or four sessions per week, over a six-month period. Sessions lasted approximately 40 minutes and students engaged in a variety of individual and group activities. An individualised deck of cards containing number problems was prepared for each student in advance of the session. The findings indicate that students benefited by participating in the intervention, with a

statistically significant difference ($g = 0.34$) on the TEMA–3 scores favouring the intervention group over the control group ($p < .001$) (Rolfhus et al., 2013).

Peltier et al. (2017) in their study on schema instruction, found both the presence and the duration of intervention to be significant – schema instruction, defined by Peltier as a systematic approach to problem solving based around organising knowledge, providing scaffolding and supporting instruction and learning. Participation in these higher-order approaches to problem solving showed significant effect sizes in these groups. The findings suggest, from a pedagogical perspective, that small-group, hands-on learning, on a regular basis had a significant positive impact on young children’s understanding of number problems. For the purpose of this report, the term mathematics difficulty (MD) is used to describe students at risk of struggling with mathematics or with persistent low mathematics performance or those who have a learning disability specific to mathematics such as dyscalculia rather than more general learning difficulties (Stevens et al., 2018). Interventions targeted at specific areas of need such as reading difficulties and English as an Additional Language contexts require attention to the learner and to mathematics, as discussed below.

Reading Difficulties and Mathematics

In the elementary grades, students with MD perform lower than peers without MD on tasks related to mathematics fluency, and exhibit low word problem-solving performance compared with students without MD (Stevens et al., 2018). As the majority of mathematics tests and standardised tests require students to read problems to demonstrate competency, it is pertinent therefore to examine performance differences following intervention between students with MD with and without reading difficulty. The findings point to the need to:

- critically select mathematics interventions;
- consider the reading profiles of students with MD;
- determine whether adaptations or supplements to the mathematics intervention are necessary based on a student’s difficulty or lack of difficulty with reading within and outside of mathematics;
- evaluate the research as to the effectiveness of the intervention prior to implementation to improve mathematics proficiency levels of students with MD (Powell et al., 2020).

The findings further indicate that students with MD and reading difficulty, and MD-alone, benefit from some versions of word-problem interventions and interventions focused on other mathematics content (Powell et al., 2020). Without an appropriate targeted intervention, mathematics skills and mathematical reasoning can continue to cause problems for students across the transition to secondary school (Stevens et al., 2018).

English as an Additional Language

Children who present in the school system with English as an Additional Language (EAL) are a heterogeneous group with varied levels of competence in or exposure to the language of instruction. Indications that this group can struggle with mathematics content (Castro-Olivo et al., 2011), have been challenged by findings that bilingual learners can achieve as well as their monolingual peers where tests are administered in their first language (Alt et al., 2013), or where the language load of mathematical tasks is reduced (Alt, 2014). Care must be taken, therefore, to ensure that comprehension of the assessment tool is not an obstacle to mathematical performance. Educators should also be clear as to the intention of interventions – are they to address language needs, or perceived mathematics needs. There is evidence that high quality mathematics teaching and learning, with a focus on conceptual understanding and mathematical discussion can serve the learning needs of EAL pupils very well (Huford-Ackles et al., 2004). Indeed a key finding of Arizmendi et al., (2021) in their systematic review of interventions to improve EAL learners' understanding and use of the language of mathematics was that most interventions follow best practices for monolingual children. In reviewing language-based interventions however, Arizmendi et al. discovered modest effect sizes for interventions based on language, with better effects noted for interventions targeted at pre-school children, for those interventions of longer duration, and for interventions with a specific focus on 'numeracy' rather than 'mixed math skills'. It would seem that a focus on the development of mathematical language alone is of limited effect in promoting mathematical performance. The dearth of studies examining interventions for EAL pupils with a focus other than the development of language skills, and the complexity of the area – as noted above with regard to the challenges of authentic and meaningful assessment constitute a need for further research in the area.

Gender

Women's underrepresentation in mathematics-related careers continues to concern policymakers and educators both in Ireland and beyond. Ghasemi et al., (2019) sought to unpack this issue on a global scale by examining a range of data from the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA) TIMSS 2015, and the World Economic Forum's Global Gender Gap Report 2017. They compared fourth grade girls and boys and discovered no statistical difference between them in terms of mathematics achievement and high achievers. This finding is corroborated by other investigations by Ghasemi and Burley (2019). They also used data from TIMSS to investigate cross-national gender differences in mathematics-related affect, again comparing fourth and eighth graders to track any differences in gender-related characteristics. The findings also suggest that mathematical achievement for boys and girls is similar and no statistically significant findings on gender emerged from their investigation. The findings from these international studies signify that gender has no significant impact on children's mathematical abilities or achievement.

Influence of Home Environment

In terms of numerical competence, children from marginalised and disadvantaged contexts such as low socioeconomic (SES) backgrounds, membership of minority groups or those habitually experiencing discrimination are more likely to enter education already at a disadvantage relative to their more privileged peers (Cason et al., 2019). The desirability of an early focus on a numerical competence grounded in conceptual understanding has been underlined, as this has been shown to be a core predictor of children's mathematical achievement throughout their school experience. Awareness of low SES has been shown to influence teachers to under assess the abilities of children (Deunk et al., 2018). Previous efforts in Ireland have seen success in improving the performance of all but not in narrowing the gap between those attending DEIS schools and their more advantaged peers (DES, 2017, p. 9). It is not unreasonable to assume that students with low SES or other marginalised status who are not attending a DEIS school may have fared no better than those who are. Therefore, the need to address the gap in mathematical competence at an early age must represent a considerable priority for future initiatives in the state, and must be prioritised in the early years.

Maths Anxiety. A significant contributing factor to children's engagement with mathematics is the negative relationship between mathematics anxiety and mathematics

achievement (Ashcraft & Moore, 2009; Ramirez et al., 2013). Choi and Han (2020) examined the relationship between parental attitudes toward mathematics and their students' mathematics anxiety. They discovered a small, though statistically significant, correlation for the relationship between students' mathematics anxiety and parents' attitudes toward mathematics (-.26). On the contrary, the findings of the meta-analysis indicate that as parents' positive attitudes toward mathematics increase, their children's anxiety decreases. Significantly, this is most prevalent in elementary and middle school students. Parental perspectives are an important indicator of children's attitudes towards mathematics and their achievement.

Homework. Homework is a complex issue, often impacted by a range of factors including the individual student, home environment and parental engagement. Fan et al., (2017) conducted a 30-year meta-analysis of the homework-achievement relationship in mathematics (and science) to examine the factors that impact the correlation between the two. They discovered a small and positive relationship between homework and student achievement in mathematics. The results suggest these findings are of greatest significance in elementary or primary school aged children (Fan et al., 2017). Parental engagement was deemed to be a significant factor in children's homework-achievement relationship.

Conclusion

This report represents a synthesis of systematic literature reviews that pertain to the factors that enable, or present barriers to, high quality numeracy pedagogy in primary school. A common thread running through all the reviews is the importance of situating the learner at the heart of the learning, and of the dynamic engagement of the entire school community in contributing to children's attitude to and achievement in numeracy rather than the sole responsibility for the learning falling exclusively to the teacher. Neither is numeracy seen as a solitary activity, carried out at discrete, scheduled time periods during the school day, with routine individual seatwork comprising generic paper-and-pencil procedural-type textbook activities. Rather, rich numeracy environments see children actively collaborating on a broad range of tasks with clearly defined learning outcomes that offer equitable access to content, a range of support tools, and provision for extension. Ultimately, this report highlights the potential of all children to have a positive learning experience and in realising their ability to achieve in numeracy.

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Appendix

Research Question

What pedagogical strategies, approaches and methodologies support numeracy development for all learners in primary schools?

Key Search Terms

S1. DE “STEM Education” (as a Subject Heading accessed via the thesaurus); S2. “STEM Education” (as a free text search, title search, abstract search as an OR search); S3. Combine S1 and S2 with OR; S4. DE "MATHEMATICS Education" (as a Subject Heading accessed via the thesaurus); S5. "MATHEMATICS Education" (as a free text search, title search, abstract search as an OR search); S6. Combine S4 and S5 with OR; S7. Combine S3 and S6 with OR; S8. “numeracy” or "math* literacy" or math* (as a free text search, title search, abstract search as an OR search); S9. Combine S7 and S8 with OR; S10. Combine S9 with “meta-analysis” or “systematic review” using AND; S11. Combine S10 with "primary school" OR "elementary school" OR "primary education" OR "elementary education" OR "K-12" OR "middle school" OR "junior high school" OR "5-12 years" OR "key stage 1" OR "key stage 2" OR "foundation level" OR "transition to school" OR "transition to post primary" OR "transition to second-level" OR "transition to secondary"

Key Data Sources Consulted

Date limit 2011 onwards, limited to ‘peer review’ and limited to English language where necessary.

Three databases were searched (a) EBSCO Education Research Complete (b) EBSCO ERIC (c) Scopus. ‘Grey’ literature was identified through hand searches.

Review	Number of studies	Effect size (If available)	Key Findings
Arizmendi, G. D., Li, J-T., L., Van Horn, M. L., Petcu, S. D., & Swanson, H.L. (2021).	Six group studies involving 15 independent samples and 3,766 participants	Overall, the mean ES of a language-based focus in intervention of mathematics for English learners in a group-study design was $g = 0.26$ ($SE = 0.07$; $k = 15$, $N = 3,766$).	Examined whether interventions focusing on teaching mathematical language to learners with English as an Additional Language (EAL) improves mathematics performance, with attention to factors such as age, method of intervention, risk factors etc. Acknowledgement that membership of the English language learners group does not automatically predict difficulties in mathematics.
Bicer, A., Chamberlin, S., & Perihan, C. (2021).	30	mean effect size was $r = 0.47$	Moderate and statistically significant ($r = 0.47$, $p < .05$) positive correlation between mathematics achievement and creativity and stronger when the relationship was examined with mathematical creativity ($r = 0.53$, $p < .05$) than with general creativity. The relationship was stronger for elementary and middle school students than for high school students.
Byun, J.H., & Joung, E. (2018).	33 studies	The overall weighted effect size, which was calculated to examine the impact of digital game based learning on learning mathematics, was 0.37.	Digital game based learning can be an effective way to improve non-cognitive aspects of learning mathematics such as interest, motivation, confidence and attitudes of primary school students. Most of the games used in the studies were related to procedural fluency only. Further investigation needs to be done on how digital games can affect students' conceptual understanding. The effectiveness of digital games on students' mathematics achievement in K-12 settings is inconclusive.

Carbonneau, K.J., Marley, S.C., & Selig, J.P. (2013).	55	The aggregated mean effect size of 0.37 was statistically significant (p .001, 95% CI [0.30, 0.44]).	Efficacy of teaching mathematics with concrete manipulatives. Findings indicate medium to large effect sizes in favour of instructional strategies that use manipulatives when compared with abstract instruction. Moderate to large effect sizes were evidenced when students were measured on higher-level outcomes, such as problem solving, transfer and justification.
Cason, M., Young, J., & Kuehnert, E. (2019).	17	39 effect sizes Cohen's d= 0.88	Interventions aimed at improving children's numerical competency are found to be effective, in particular interventions in the early years. The effect size is reduced in interventions with children in the later stages of primary school, therefore early intervention focused on improving understanding is key. Given the prevalence of underdeveloped number competencies in children from disadvantaged socio-economic backgrounds, interventions focusing on number competency is highly desirable for these children too.
Choi, J. & Han, H. (2020).	7	Random effects weighted average effect size was $r = -0.26$ ($p < 0.001$)	The average correlation for the relationship between students' mathematics anxiety and parents' attitudes toward mathematics was -0.26, a small, though statistically significant, correlation. The inverse relationship indicates that as parents' positive attitudes toward mathematics increase, their children's anxiety decreases. Most prevalent in elementary and middle school students.

<p>Deunk, M.I., Smale-Jacobse, A.E., deBoer, H., Doolaard, S., & Bosker, R.J. (2018).</p>	<p>21 studies</p>	<p>D values Overall -0.065 Low ability -0.300* Average ability -0.161 High ability -0.112</p>	<p>Specific primary focus and on language for L1 instruction, looked at ability grouping (within class and between class), use of computerised systems and differentiation as part of whole school action. Results show small to moderate effects of computerised systems and whole school action, and little for any form of ability grouping.</p>
<p>Fan, H., Xu, J., Cai, Z., He, J., & Fan, X. (2017).</p>	<p>28</p>	<p>Effect-size based meta-analysis (k= 61), the overall relationship between math homework and math Performance was $r = 0.221$, with 95% confidence interval ranging from 0.191 to 0.250.</p>	<p>The results suggest that the relationship between homework and performance in mathematics appeared to be stronger for elementary grades. Overall small and positive relationship between homework and student achievement in math.</p>

Graham, S., Kiuahara, S., & MacKay, M. (2020).	56 total with 21 experiments (38% of studies) assessing the impact of writing on mathematics	effect size = 0.32	<p>Writing for learning about mathematics content material can be a useful tool for promoting mathematics learning.</p> <p>This pedagogical practice is most effective in classrooms where writing for learning is valued.</p> <p>There was no statistically significant difference by grade (elementary or middle school) so writing for learning in mathematics can be utilised throughout primary education.</p>
Kul, Ü., Çelik, S., & Aksu, Z. (2018).	54	Average effect size is 1.047 (p<0.05)	Using materials in mathematics has a positive and high influence on achievement.
Merritt, J., Lee, M.Y., Rillero, P., & Kinach, B.M. (2017).	9	Not provided	Problem based learning is an effective method for improving K–8 students' academic achievement, including knowledge retention, conceptual development, and attitudes.

<p>Peltier, C. & Vannest, KJ. (2017).</p>	<p>21 Studies</p>	<p>Overall effect size (Hedges g) of 1.57</p>	<p>A meta-analysis on the effect of schema instruction on the solving word problems of elementary school students including efforts to identify variables that may moderate effects. The overall effects ($g = 1.57$, $SE = .043$, for immediate Problem solving; $g = 1.09$, $SE = .046$, for transfer Problem Solving) suggest on average, schema instruction improved immediate and transfer PS performance. Findings suggest that schema instruction produces larger effects than other instructional methods analyzed in previous meta-analyses. Previous meta-analyses identified only a limited number of approaches.</p>
<p>Powell, S.R., Doabler, C.T., Akinola, O.A., Therrien, W.J., Maddox, S.A., & Hess, K.E. (2020).</p>	<p>65</p>	<p>The ESs from the word-problem studies with Mathematics Difficulty (MD) + Reading Difficulty (RD) students were much higher (e.g., 4.48, 1.83, 1.80, 1.56, 1.53, 1.34) than any of the reported ESs from the studies with MD alone students. E.g., The largest reported ES from a word-problem intervention with MD-alone students was 0.67.</p>	<p>30% to 70% of students with mathematics difficulty also experience difficulty with reading.</p> <p>The majority of high-stakes mathematics tests require students to read problems to demonstrate mathematics competency. Standardised tests may provide an incomplete profile of students when the likely interaction of reading difficulty with mathematics difficulty is ignored.</p> <p>Students with mathematics difficulty in the elementary grades with or without reading difficulty demonstrated improved mathematics performance following interventions targeted at improving mathematics.</p>

Rolfhus, E., Clarke, B., Decker, L.E., Williams, C., & Domino, J. (2013).	9 studies reviewed (1 met all criteria n=2719 students)	Statistically significant difference ($g= 0.34$) on the TEMA-3 scores favouring the intervention group over the control group ($p < .001$)	Main finding is that students at risk for difficulties in grade 1 mathematics benefited by participating in the intervention programme Number Rockets
Sokolowski, A., Li, Y., & Willson, V. (2015).	24	Moderate effect size (ES) = 0.60, SE = 0.03. A 95% confidence interval around the overall mean - Clower = 0.53 and Cupper = 0.66 - indicated nonzero population effect and relative precision.	A moderator analysis revealed differences among the effects on student achievement in Grades 1 to 8 between traditional mathematics problem solving approaches and exploratory computerized environments, favouring the latter.
Sokolowski, A. (2018).	13 studies, 1941 subjects	ES =0.53 (SE +0.05)	'The ultimate question that was posited in this study was what representations are the most accessible to an elementary math student'. Findings include that including representations in mathematics teaching is beneficial to children, and that effect size increases as duration of intervention increases.

Vetter, M., Orr, R., O'Dwyer, N., & O'Connor, H. (2019).	Systematic review of 6 randomized controlled trials & 5 quasi-experimental studies evaluating 4082 participants (53% girls; mean age 7.5-11.1 years)	Math scores were significantly better in the intervention group in 6 of 11 studies on at least 1 test (ES: 0.42-4.7; $p \leq .03$).	Study focused on the effectiveness of active learning that combines physical activity and mathematics in schoolchildren. Mathematics scores were significantly better in the intervention group in 6 of 11 studies on at least 1 test.
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